

PRESINMED

“Preserving the singularity of Mediterranean high-mountain biodiversity hotspots: a NbS approach”

Stakeholder Integration and Governance Manual

Methodological approach and planning for stakeholder integration and governance model for NbS to preserve biodiversity hotspots

To cite this manual

Moreno-Llorca, R.A., Martínez-López, J., Martín Civantos, J.M., Sella, L., Alcaraz-Segura, D., Zamora R. (2025). Methodological approach and planning for stakeholder integration and governance model for NbS to preserve biodiversity hotspots. PRESINMED Stakeholder integration and governance. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183113>

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1. Introduction

Stakeholder engagement is a fundamental step of trans-disciplinary research activities, aiming at involving social actors in the co-creation of knowledge and shared sustainable management solutions. Through this process, we will learn about the historical relationship between humans and nature, local ecological knowledge, co-evolutive processes, adaptation and resilience, but also about conflicts, human complexity, policies, economy, identities, and memories, that shape the social-ecological systems. Conservation cannot be understood without the human factor, including past uses and practices and current changes and challenges.

Stakeholder engagement and shared governance are cornerstones in PRESINMED, aiming at preserving and restoring wet meadows by means of Nature-based solutions (NbS) that will be co-designed, co-produced and governed with all relevant stakeholders (i.e., park managers, scientists, livestock farmers, local communities, tourism companies, NGOs). This alliance between researchers and stakeholders (a science-policy working group or Community of Practice; CoP) will foster active participation of stakeholders in each case study, so that it can generate real change that can be sustained after the project.

Nature based Solutions (NbS) are approaches that leverage biodiversity and ecosystems to address major societal challenges, providing knowledge, tools, and solutions for conservation and sustainable management.

One of the principals aims of Biodiversa+ is to develop nature-based solutions for tackling major societal challenges. This involves providing policy makers and other stakeholders with adequate knowledge, tools, and solutions to conserve and restore biodiversity and ecosystems, and to better manage biodiversity to deliver a range of ecosystem services.

Following tasks 3.1 and 3.5, stakeholder engagement and related activities will be developed at the case study level. After an initial mapping of relevant stakeholders, face-to-face workshops and interviews will be organized to

collect key information and implement the co-designing and co-production processes of NbS. In particular, these activities are aimed to: (a) inform relevant stakeholders about PRESINMED objectives and discuss preliminary outcomes, variables, indicators and methods; (b) better align the project with stakeholders' real needs and profit from their expert field knowledge and data about the most relevant management issues; (c) select area to perform the activities foreseen; (d) select the most informative and managerially relevant essential variables (field-based and remote sensing-based) to be monitored in the project .

It is very important to consider personal data protection in the development of the project, especially in tasks that involve different stakeholder profiles. All participants in surveys, interviews or workshops must understand and complete Annexes I (Information sheet for participants) and II (Written consent of the participant), which are customised for each study site and responsible institution.

The knowledge acquired in PRESINEMD will be transferred to the CoP to promote sustainable agriculture, livestock and ecotourism activities.

Hence, tasks 3.1 and 3.5 are deeply related and will rely on common methodologies.

This guide is a roadmap for local case study teams to:

- Map relevant stakeholders for PRESINMED purposes (sec. 2)
- Extract preliminary information concerning traditional uses and local ecological knowledge and governance systems (sec. 3)
- Start the CoP (sec. 4)

2. Stakeholder mapping: creating the community of practice

Biodiversa manuals provide comprehensive guidance on stakeholder mapping (see [Annex III](#)), which is a crucial initial step for effective engagement in research projects, particularly within the context of biodiversity and ecosystem services. The goal of stakeholder mapping is to identify, categorise, and understand relevant stakeholders. This process helps researchers determine who needs to be engaged, how many stakeholders there are, and the most successful methods of engagement, depending on the research focus, potential outcomes, impacts, and available resources.

A stakeholder is defined as any person or group who influences or is influenced by the research. This broad definition includes anyone directly or indirectly affected by a project, or those with an interest or ability to influence its outcome, positively or negatively.

Stakeholder identification is a critical step because participant selection significantly influences the outcomes of an engagement process. Effective representation can foster learning and trust, while unrepresentative selection may lead to negative social outcomes, increased conflict, ineffective projects.

PRESINMED partners will build a Community of Practice made up of all relevant stakeholders involved in each study area. The Community needs to be built around the idea of developing NbS approaches to preserve biodiversity hotspots (core of the PRESINMED project). This involves a series of stages (figure 1):

1. Identify the relevant stakeholders within each of the existing stakeholder profiles. It is important to cover as many categories as possible.
2. Categorise stakeholders based on their interest in NbS and influence capacity and the type of collaboration you would like to establish (see table 1).

3. Compile information about the relationships among the stakeholders identified, their attitudes towards the project, their willingness to engage and ways to communicate with them.

Figure 1. Stages to map stakeholders. Source: Adapted from Durham et al., 2014

2.1. Stage 1: Methods for identifying key stakeholders

The first stage emphasizes inclusivity, ensuring all individuals or groups affected by, influencing, or interested in the research are considered. Researchers should consider what stakeholders can contribute and what motivates their involvement (Durham et al., 2014).

- Systematic Approaches:
 - Ex-ante approach: Stakeholders are identified in advance based on predefined categories, such as:

- Protected area managers and personnel
 - Local or regional governments
 - Non-governmental organisations (NGOs)
 - Social associations such as voluntary networks or mountaineering clubs
 - Business and industry
 - Local populations
 - Landowners and managers
 - Professional groups
 - Researchers working in relevant disciplines
 - Educators
 - Students
- Ad-hoc approach (Snowball Sampling): This is an iterative process, usually performed after the ex-ante approach, where initial contacts identify further stakeholders until no new ones are found. Existing networks and previous project partners are valuable starting points.
- Key Considerations: Researchers should consider who is responsible for decisions, affected by research outputs, interested in results, able to provide information/resources, likely to hold negative views, and who is essential or preferable to involve.
- Tools for Identification (use the ones more relevant in your case study):
- Brainstorming with other organizations that have been involved in similar activities or those working in similar locations.
 - Consulting with colleagues to share knowledge about who may have an interest in the research.
 - Developing a 'mind map' (figure 2) that can be used to identify suitable stakeholders, assessing secondary data (e.g. historical records, media articles).

- Utilizing existing lists of organizations to identify specific groups, networks and agencies who represent relevant elements of society.

To identify and characterise stakeholders, you can collect the data presented by using the [following template](#) (Hover your mouse over the header of each column to understand how to fill in the data).

Figure 2: Example of stakeholder mind map, adapted from the Forestry Commission (Durham et al., 2014).

2.2. Stage 2: Assess, analyze, and prioritize stakeholders

Not every stakeholder requires the same level of engagement, so prioritization helps focus resources efficiently.

- Interest-Influence Matrix: This widely used tool (Tharwat, 2018) plots stakeholders based on their interest in the project versus their influence on it:
 - Collaborate (High Interest – High Influence): These stakeholders are most beneficial for engagement, offering information, permissions, and resources, and are significantly impacted by outcomes. Full, active partnership is appropriate.
 - Involve (High Influence – Low Interest): Influential but may be difficult to engage due to low interest or capacity. Significant early effort is needed to involve them.
 - Consult (High Interest – Low Influence): Supportive but lack direct capacity to significantly help the project. They may become influential by forming alliances. Special attention may be needed to empower them.
 - Inform (Low Interest – Low Influence): These should be monitored and kept updated with tailored, objective information.

To fulfil the Interest-Influence Matrix, please use the [following template](#).

- Tailoring Engagement Levels: Based on this matrix, engagement can be tailored:
 - Inform: Update interested parties with balanced, objective, and tailored information.
 - Consult: Obtain feedback and provide information on design, methodologies, analysis, and outcomes.
 - Involve: Work directly throughout the project lifecycle to understand and incorporate their concerns and aspirations into decision-making.
 - Collaborate: Work in partnership, including co-development of methods and solutions.

For categorising stakeholders into ‘High Dedication’ and ‘Low Dedication’ depending upon perceptions of the project and perceived goals, please use the [following template](#).

2.3. Stage 3: Understand your stakeholders.

Gathering detailed information helps tailor engagement strategies.

- Key Information to Gather:
 - Existing relationships between the project and stakeholders, and among stakeholders.
 - Knowledge relevant to the project.
 - Likely views (positive or negative) about the project and potential for conflict.
 - Appropriate means of communication, adapted for specific groups.
 - Willingness and capacity to engage, and any barriers (technical, physical, linguistic, geographical, political, time, information, or knowledge).
- Tabulation: This information can be tabulated, potentially combined with the interest-influence matrix.
- Understanding Relationships: Methods to analyze social networks, map stakeholder perceptions and values, and assess conflicts (Boix-Fayos et al., 2023) are useful to understand how different groups interact and identify key individuals for knowledge diffusion.

To document the information to understand your stakeholders, please use the [following template](#).

2.4. Practical Considerations and Challenges in Stakeholder Mapping

Biodiversa manuals emphasize several practicalities and challenges:

- **Early Engagement:** Most researchers find value in engaging stakeholders as early as possible, ideally at the project initial stage, to ensure a sense of ownership and influence on research design. Early input helps refine research questions and ensures relevance.
- **Managing Expectations:** Policymakers often operate on shorter timescales and seek quick, certain solutions, which can conflict with the complex, uncertain nature of research outcomes. Researchers should explicitly discuss expectations from the outset to manage these differences.
- **Stakeholder Fatigue:** This can occur when communities are overloaded with engagement activities that do not lead to tangible outcomes. To mitigate this, researchers should ensure clear benefits for engagement and work with opinion leaders to encourage participation. Stakeholders need to be involved in a well-defined and limited number of activities in the project. Better to avoid involvement in simultaneous activities from different projects.
- **Resources and Expertise:** Effective engagement requires proper funding and management, ideally by individuals with training or experience in stakeholder engagement. Including social scientists or professional facilitators on the research team can be beneficial, especially in conflict-prone situations.
- **Data and communication Plan:** A detailed data and communication plan of the expected project outputs is essential, including arrangements for data sharing and access, demonstrating how it enhances policy makers' and other stakeholders' capacity to use research information. Communication of activities needs to be organized on time using clear and synthetic material.
- **Adaptability:** Engagement plans should remain flexible and adaptable, evolving as the project progresses and as researchers learn more about

stakeholder dynamics, alliances, and potential conflicts. This includes tailoring communication to local cultures and customs.

- Citizen Science: This approach can involve non-experts in data collection, raising awareness, providing new skills, and empowering volunteers. It can supplement traditional data collection but requires significant time and effort for effective engagement and data quality assurance.
- Local knowledge: The more we know about the territory and traditional practices, the better our interactions with stakeholders will be. It is good to know place names or any historical or cultural references that our informants may use during the interview workshops.

3. Preparatory work for the first workshop: semi-structured interviews on traditional uses and local ecological knowledge and governance systems

Based on this 3-stage mapping, the local teams need to select the key informants to involve in the planned workshops.

In particular, the first face-to-face interviews are aimed at gaining information about a) traditional uses, local ecological knowledge, governance systems, and b) perceptions of land use changes and impacts of livestock, recreation activities, and climate change.

Follow these steps to prepare for the preliminary interviews:

- (1) For the preparatory interviews, we will select key informants: Who are the people who know the most about these issues in the territory? We can also ask the stakeholders identified in the previous task who are the local people who best know the territory, the customs, the forms

of work and management. Additionally, it is advisable to interview other people who, because of their life or professional background, can offer a different point of view. Interviews can also be organized online, better if conducted in the stakeholder's mother tongue.

- (2) Optionally, record the interview (advisable but optional): We will ask the interviewee's permission to record the session, and it will normally be necessary for them to sign the consent form (see Annex I and II) or to declare the consent at the beginning of the recording.
- (3) Preparation of the contents of the interview: This step is essential and needs to be carefully addressed in advance. A semi-structured interview has a battery of questions (see section 3.1), which should follow a logic based on our interests, the type of information we are trying to obtain and the previous knowledge we have. It may be useful to have some control questions to confirm some of the information (e.g. by asking the same question in a different way). This battery of questions is not closed but serves to guide the interview. From there, the interviewee should be left free to move on to other topics or to introduce other aspects that may be interesting or that may make the interviewee feel more comfortable. Often these are anecdotes or life stories, from which information can also be extracted. Select from section 3.1 the most suitable questions for your case study.
- (4) Start the interview: In the beginning, briefly introduce the project and the aim of the interview and then start asking the list of questions you have selected. All answers from the interview can be added in a spreadsheet via a survey or Google form that can be filled in by the interviewer.
- (5) Development of the interview: Create a space of trust that allows for dialogue. It is not an interrogation, but a conversation. The more natural it is, the better the result will be. It is important that the interviewee can detach from the strict answering of questions and that

the interview can move on to new topics or that he/she can tell anecdotes and life stories. When appropriate, you can return to the set of questions or to the main thread of the interview, trying not to force the situation and having patience. A good interviewer will know how to adapt to the situation and redirect the interview when necessary. You can insist and cross-examine certain aspects in different ways in order to be sure of the answers or to obtain confirmation of certain information. In the end, please check that you have collected all the relevant information according to your objectives (see next step).

- (6) Alternatively, interviews can be substituted by telephone calls or online questionnaires, in case it is very difficult to engage with stakeholders initially.

3.1. Content of the interviews/workshop.

I. Basic information about the person and wet meadows:

1. What is your name? Age? Dedication?
2. What relationship do you have with [Sierra Nevada] (or with the high peaks)? How long is this relationship?
3. How would you describe a wet meadow? How would you describe it?
4. Is it natural? What role have local populations played in its creation or maintenance?
5. Are there current and/or traditional uses of the wet meadows? What has it traditionally been used for?

II. Information on traditional land uses and local ecological knowledge:

6. Has the pasture been managed historically (e.g. last 20-50 years) by shepherds? How has the sheep/goats/cattle pasture been managed historically? [if no specific historical period is under investigation, let each stakeholder choose the reference

period but always remember to take note of it – it applies also to the subsequent questions]

7. How has the mountain water been managed in the past? Is the shape of lakes or watercourses in the study area natural? Are there ditches or other management actions/infrastructures? [always remember to ask the reference period to each stakeholder]
8. How has the soil been managed (cleaning, clearing, fertilisation)?
9. How have the plants and grasses been managed?
10. What impact have the traditional uses (livestock) or have had on the high mountain pastures?
11. What carrying capacity do you think the wet meadow has in relation to pressures, such as livestock or mountain tourists?
12. What is the relationship between wild and domestic herbivores?
13. What kind of livestock has there been historically?
14. What historical changes have there been in livestock type, numbers or management (try to specify dates and numbers)? Do you know data sources or statistics that can help?
15. What is the ownership of the wet meadows (i.e. public or private)? How is it currently managed, who can use it and how?
16. Are there some specific ecotourism (wildlife, adventure, rural, geotourism, etc.) activities offered in the area? If so, who is offering them?

III. Information on perceptions of changes in use, new uses and impacts of livestock, recreation activities and Climate Change:

17. What changes of use have you observed in recent decades (e.g. last 20-50 years) in the high mountain pastures? What activities are currently being developed?
18. What is the relationship between stockbreeding and the conservation policies of the Protected Area?

19. Which are the most common recreational activities in the area?
What impact do recreational activities have on high mountain pastures?
20. What is the relationship between stockbreeding and recreational (e.g. hiking) activities? Are they compatible?
21. What is the relationship between leisure activities and the conservation policies of the Protected Area?
22. What impact does Climate Change have on traditional uses (pastures, water availability, etc.)?
23. What impact does Climate Change have on recreational activities in the high mountains?

4. Preliminary contents and objectives of the first workshop

The first workshop of the project for each case study should take place as soon as possible, no later than January 2026. The overall idea of the workshop is to start a CoP, discuss the preliminary findings about the socio-ecological context of each study site and start identifying and co-designing NbS (Catalano et al., 2025). The use of online live collaboration tools (e.g., Miro, Mentimeter, Excalidraw) can help facilitate the workshop.

A draft agenda of the meeting, which should not last more than 3-4 hours in total (including breaks), could be as follows:

1. Introduction to the project (15')
2. Ice-breaker (15'): Self round of introduction answering the question: What is your favourite landscape and why?
3. Definition and examples of wet meadows and Nature Based Solutions (15')
4. General short socio-ecological characterization of the case study (15')
5. Coffee-break (15')

6. Break-out groups to discuss about 3 topics:
 - a. Local-ecological knowledge and traditional land uses (20')
 - b. Impacts of climate change, tourism and livestock (20')
 - c. Identification and co-design of NbS adapted to the specific case study and (20')
7. Short break (15')
8. Sharing of each group's discussions (by representatives) with the rest of the group (1 h)
9. Plenary discussion and main conclusions per topic (a-c) (15')
10. Questions, open challenges and next steps (15')

5. Provisional timeline of activities for tasks 3.1 and 3.5.

Figure 3 shows a timeline of the project activities related to stakeholders engagement during 2025 and early 2026.

Figure 3: Distribution of activities related to tasks 3.1 and 3.5 in the coming months.

6. References

- Boix-Fayos, C., Martínez-López, J., Albaladejo, J., de Vente, J., 2023. Finding common grounds for conflict resolution through value analysis of stakeholders around the socio-ecological crisis of the Mar Menor coastal lagoon (Spain). *Landscape and Urban Planning* 238, 104829. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2023.104829>
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Annex I: Information sheet for participants

To access Annex I visit this [LINK](#).

Annex II: Written consent of the participant

To access Annex II visit this [LINK](#).

Annex III: BiodivERsA manuals

To access Annex III visit this [LINK](#).